

Considerations Leading to Powerful and More Inclusive VLE

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Prior to the COVID pandemic, the K-12 educational landscape offered virtual learning environments (VLE) in a selective and limited scope. Those students that fared well had strong literacy skills, self-motivation and academic talents (Johnson et al., 2023). The same profile of successful students in the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), also excelled in the traditional brick-and-mortar school. Since the global pandemic, the world has changed, and educators found their way into VLE with increasing regularity. We have seen that many students can manage within the VLE, but just managing will not suffice when we are looking at the long-term effects on students' educational opportunities (McHolm, 2023).

Growing research has amassed that examines technological adoption in education particularly in higher education (Appiah & Van Tonder, 2018; Maymon, et al., 2018; Schmid, et al., 2014; Walter, et al., 2018). Less research has focused on the educational outcomes for students in the K-12 setting until the pandemic (Whalen, 2021). Further less still, have investigated academic achievement and digital assessment in the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) (Caprara & Caprara, 2022). Despite these apparent gaps in research, the emerging findings during the pandemic has bolstered its examination by many educators and leaders (Shamir-Inbal & Blau, 2021; Whalen, 2021). This article acts as a continuance of this work.

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Fuelling this work, are governmental requirements for publicly funded school systems to have virtual learning options across Canada. As of 2019, there were 268 e-learning programs offered within Canada for K-12 students (Barbour & LaBonte, 2020). With 9 of 13 provinces/territories having legislation to address e-learning for the K-12 environment, this work is of growing importance. Back then, 5,056,819 students were engaged in publicly funded e-learning (Barbour & LaBonte, 2020, p. 9). In 2022, that number rose slightly to 5.3 million students (Barbour, 2023). (Although a notable increase, it is not the growth that one might expect with widespread exposure to VLE during the pandemic. I wonder if the experiences of disenfranchised students kept these numbers from ballooning more extensively). More recently, school districts in Ontario are responding to the Ministry of Education's changes to high school compulsory VLE credits beginning in 2024. Therefore, understanding what teachers need to do to provide strong educational opportunities within the K-12 context will be the focus of this article. Initially I will explore fundamentals of good virtual learning environments, then contrast the TPACK and PICRAT frameworks, considering their strengths and limitations. Looking for ways to enhance inclusivity will be an undercurrent of this article. Finally, I will consolidate my critical reflections for educators within the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE). This article offers models and tools that can help educators within the VLE context to develop the approaches necessary to reach more diverse student needs in a responsive way. The purpose of this article is to provoke your thinking about the decisions we make within the VLE to meet the needs of all learners.

Limitations

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This article will not address the well-documented disadvantages to those with poor internet connectivity, insufficient technology support (Kieviet, 2023), antiquated/inadequate devices (Hardman, 2020; Sider et al., 2021) or asynchronous learning environment (Whitehead, 2023).

There are many barriers known for inclusive virtual environments in the form of socio-economic constraints (Oz & Kala, 2023). The pandemic also highlighted how marginalized groups were found to be further disadvantaged when the world shifted to remote learning (Gallagher-Mackay et al., 2021). It cannot be understated that all educators have a responsibility to redress the glaring inequities experienced during the pandemic. It is our duty to remove systemic barriers experienced by Indigenous, racialized, 2SILGBTQ++, and neurodivergent learners (Jackson et al., 2021; Katz, Sokal & Wu, 2021; Masta, 2018). All students must find enriching educational opportunities within public education (Laplanche Carey, 2019; Masta, 2018). Although significant and worthy of deep discourse, these realities exceed the scope of this article.

Differences and Similarities of the Learning Environment

Learning requires effort, discovery and rehearsal. When done well, all learners can enter into the learning environment inclusively. When done haphazardly, many students are left behind. The VLE is the same. When done well, it can be a safe and inclusive learning environment. When done without deep consideration of the learner profiles, strengths and needs, the VLE will disadvantage many (Michel, Pierrot & Solari-Landa, 2021) further perpetuating the disproportionate negative impact seen within the remote learning phase of the pandemic (Gallagher-Mackay et al., 2021; Sider et al., 2021). Despite this reality, the VLE can showcase some advantages over brick-and-

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mortar schools (Hantoobi, et al., 2021). From a differentiation perspective, the VLE can act to provide accommodations for learners in a seamless manner. Proximal learning becomes precision learning, but in a traditional classroom, students tend to hide their lagging skills from peers. They obfuscate through negative behaviour or distraction. But in the VLE that is not required because of the ease of differentiation. Giving what the student needs becomes a private accommodation. As educators, we need to be thoughtful and pragmatic in our VLE's. As VLE's are here to stay, we need to ensure that there is an equity of opportunity and success, regardless of a student's intersectionality and social location.

The First Digital Spaces and Now Today

Thinking related to pedagogy and assessment in the virtual environment dates back to 1990's. With the advent of emergent technology, Chickering and Ehrmann (1996) proposed that student-teacher interaction, student collaboration, active learning, prompt feedback, time on task, high expectation and respect for diverse talents and differentiation were key building effective and engaging virtual classrooms. The national Survey of Student Engagement (NSSE, 2017) confirmed that these principles continued to hold true in Canada and the United States. Theories of Self-determination (Deci & Ryan, 2003) and Flow (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997) were cited as catalysts for engagement levels when combined with the right amount of challenge in the learning (Bagroacik-Yilmaz, 2023). In the VLE, autonomy is built into the construct of the classroom. A teacher cannot engage a student that is not online. Therefore, teachers require to build their classrooms in such a way that they invite learners to engage. Universal Design Learning (UDL) principles permit all

students to find their *flow* (the right amount of challenge as to inspire without the frustration towards futility or apathy resulting from boredom) (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997). The Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) must consider how educators organize their content delivery, utilise their engagement strategies, share the lesson's learning goals, reflects the assessment criteria and outlines their feedback processes. Because the VLE can explicitly include all of these attributes, it has the possibility of being both engaging and enriching for some students. The masterful leveraging of technology in the VLE classroom holds promise in the post-pandemic world (Harris & Jones, 2021; Willermark, 2021).

Building Engagement

In the virtual learning environment, building student connection and engagement is more complex than in the in-person environment. Relationship building must be intentional and precise. In the virtual environment, you don't hear what the students are talking about as they are waiting in the hallway to come into your classroom. You don't see them playing and interacting on the school yard. For the most part, you don't see them in extracurricular activities beyond those that you personally run. Therefore, building relationships must be intentional.

In both in-person and virtual learning environments, building connection between teachers and students and between peers fosters the inclusion, safety and trust of the classroom. Before learning can occur, students must feel safe, seen and supported (Desautels, 2020). In the virtual setting these conditions for learning are equally fundamental. Deep reflection on building relationships practices with the students of the classroom, while at the same time utilizing evidence-based

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pedagogical understandings within a subject or course's content knowledge is essential within the VLE (Chusni, Saputro, & Rahardjo, 2020; Hollingshead & Carr-Chellman, 2019). The action of building relationships through 2 by 10 (spending 2 minutes for 10 consecutive days just chatting with a student), finding out their interests and building that into the learning context, attending student events outside of your classroom time, noticing things that they are proud of (i.e., a new shirt, a hairdo that they spent time on, an interesting piece of artwork in the background) all can lead to better relationships with students. The “what” of building relationships is the same in both brick-and-mortar schools and virtual classrooms. The “how” by which an educator creates these inclusive VLE are different from traditional in-person classrooms.

How do We Maximize Technology Attributes in the VLE?

Teacher-centred knowledge about sound pedagogical thinking, welcoming learning environments and building connections remain foundational in the VLE (Bagroacki-Yilmaz, 2023). We also know that with rapid technology advancement, greater opportunities for both students and teachers present almost daily. This article will provide specific examples of tools to assist in the VLE but it is not the intention of the author to endorse specific programs. The rate of which Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) is advancing in the educational landscape is almost incomprehensible, alone (Grassini, 2023). The possible changes to providing student feedback through GAI could lead to both improved or less authentic learning (acknowledging challenges to track actual student learning) (Grassini, 2023). Therefore, examples will be used merely as a snapshot in time. This

article outlines the critical analysis process that educators must do as they create, adjust and adapt to the changing needs of the students in their VLE.

The Role of Technology in the VLE

First and foremost, how technology is used to deliver educational opportunities must be considered. Mishra and Koehler originally developed the TPACK framework in 2006 to explore how technological knowledge/skills, pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge overlap and interplay with each other. Its purpose is to look at how teachers use technology in the classroom. TPACK has been used as a way for pre-service teachers to reflect on the *what, how* and *why* of using technology in their teaching instruction. Although not originally developed for applications in only VLE settings, it has clear applicability. In any Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), it is critical to maintain strong pedagogical knowledge approaches when delivering content (Mishra, 2019). In the same breath, there are weaknesses to the TPACK framework. Despite notable limitations to the TPACK framework (Cherner & Smith, 2017; Maor, 2013; Saubern, 2020, Zhang & Tang, 2021), it also offers several thoughtful parameters for consideration.

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Figure One: TPACK Framework

The TPACK framework stresses the interconnected nature of the three areas within teaching, particularly relevant to the VLE. The TPACK Venn diagram depicts how the teacher's content decisions have clear implications to what technology should be employed and what pedagogical considerations must be made. Each decision impacts the other knowledge domains. The TPACK framework has relevance and strength for teachers in the virtual learning environment. Less optimally, it does not show the connection to student voice and culturally responsive and relevant teaching practices (CRRP). For the purpose of this article, we will add the CRRP foundational elements into Content Knowledge. Considerations for student voice (absent in the framework) will be overlaid onto the Pedagogical Knowledge domain. An additional critique of this model suggests

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that it is too theoretical for some educators as terminology overlaps in ways that convolutes what the educator must do (Sauber, 2020).

Noting the academic nature of the framework, scholars have attempted to add clarity and update aspects within the framework. Lee and Kim (2014), for example, added the model to include a pedagogical approach that included five additional features for pre-service teachers to consider.

This involved a process to introduce, demonstrate, develop, implement, reflect and revise work.

This somewhat cumbersome addition to the original framework, does address how teachers should plan through a reiterative process within the pedagogical knowledge component. Within the VLE, it remains important that a process of content development and students' engagement therein is then assessed by the teacher. Upon reflection, the teacher is then able to revise their lesson planning, thereby enhancing the learning of their students. This model focuses on the teacher's knowledge and skill development.

Despite its shortcomings, TPACK still acts as a helpful to guide for teachers to select appropriate technology for the appropriate skill development of the student. Through reflection, the teacher's self-awareness will increase and their pedagogical decision making will align with the skills that they are developing in their students. TPACK has had many revisions. Meaningful revisions have included the voices of students. The balance between a student-centred voice and educator driven methods for assessments, can make this model useful for any teacher, but especially for those working in the VLE.

PICRAT Matrix as a Framework in the Virtual Classroom

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The PICRAT model, by contrast, focuses on the students' relationship with technology. This matrix was introduced to provide a theoretical framework that explores how different types of pedagogical decisions impacts the types of learning outcomes and assessment practices related to them. This model, developed by Kimmons and colleagues (2020) link technological choices with student skills being developed. This model is favoured by some (Asim et al., 2022; Ertmer, et al., 1999; Hughes, Thomas & Scharber, 2006) over TPACK because it looks at both students' relationship with technology and how the teacher's intended use of technology changes pedagogical decisions (Hughes, Thomas & Scharber, 2006).

PICRAT is an acronym that runs along the y- axis. It stands for Passive, Interactive and Creative along axis and Replacement, Amplification and Transformation along the x-axis. The tasks that we require students to complete will dictate how we assess them. Conversely, the backwards design from culminating tasks, will dictate the types of tasks that we will provide to build those skills. The PICRAT Model is a framework that focuses on the student and naturally requires the educator to reflect on their planning decisions, the purpose of individual tasks and which skills the students are developing in order to complete the given the task. Equally important, the teacher must excogitate questions of time, quality of digital tools being employed and the ability to provide feedback consistent with curricular expectations across a variety of possible student products. Using the PICRAT framework, the VLE teacher can plan a variety of tasks and assessments.

Figure 2: PICRAT Model.

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Kimmons, R., Graham, C., & West, R. (2020).

A strength of this model is that the PICRAT matrix recognises that all nine types of learning tasks are found in the VLE. By classifying the task on the matrix, an educator can reflect upon the skills that the student is developing. Wang (2023) suggested that the PICRAT model will turn passive learners into interactive and creative learners. Even when the learning task is more passive, it clearly allows the teacher to reflect on if this is best form of learning at that time. For example, watching a video (PR) can provide introductory information for a student and be an appropriate choice for content delivery. The balance of different types of learning tasks must be regularly assessed by the teacher. Cross pollinating SAMR (Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, Redefinition) framework with Bloom's Taxonomy (knowledge, understanding, application,

analysis, evaluation and synthesis), PICRAT considers the type of student learning and engagement in order to complete the task.

As a task moves further to the right-hand top of the matrix, a higher level of thinking is required by the student. Although a Transformative and Creative task is considered the highest form of student learning, the PICRAT matrix recognises the importance of other types of classroom activities, particularly those in the VLE. A mixture of teaching and learning opportunities are necessary in a classroom to keep it engaging for all students. It is part of the teacher's role to reflect on the balance between high-level thinking tasks and lower quadrant learning opportunities in the classroom. Culminating tasks should involve more creativity and amplification or transformation to really stretch the learner. Documents shared within digital sharing platforms allow students to collaborate, edit, and provide feedback whilst the teacher being able to track all changes to the document. This level of transformation could not be done without the advances in technological products.

The vertical axis of passive, interactive and creative indicate the degree of student autonomy.

Passive is something like watching a video or listening to a podcast. Interactive, is by definition, a task that requires the student to respond or relate to the content they are learning. This could include manipulating simulations or playing interactive computerized games. Creative-Transformative (CT) tasks require the student to structure their own learning. Properly formulated inquiry-based learning often necessitates the learner to manipulate, construct and problem solve, independent of the teacher. Aligning with Bloom's Taxonomy, CT work results in the learner

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synthesizing new information together to create a deeper understanding than the individual parts of the content.

Within the VLE, teachers must make many choices about the digital tools and resources they use.

Unlike in-person resources such as printed textbooks, digital resources can be changed quickly

(Bishop, 2021). Digital resources are also more inclusive. They allow for easier translation to

Braille, sizing changes, other languages and summarizing adaptive tools. Having a critical eye to

the digital resources that we select is as important as it is when working through publishers

(Rhines et al., 2021). The misinformation or the slanted perspectives found in many readily

available digital resources can often not be appropriately discerned by most students (Moyer,

2022). Teacher curated resources, although time consuming, acts as an important safeguard to the

sophisticated presentations of false or biased information. For this reason, educators must use a

clear criterion before selecting digital resources (Mignardi & Sturge, 2021; Moyer, 2022).

Online educational environments require the careful consideration of technological choices -- the

digital resources. How students interact with these choices influence educational outcomes.

Developing critical reflections, and the ability to spot “deep fakes” abundant in social media

information sources is of increasing importance in digital literacy. Once again, the ever-growing

presence of AI stands to stretch the thinking of students and teachers alike. Equally as important to

note, an educator’s tasks developed for the VLE will act as the precursor to establishing a

responsive program; inspiring creativity and higher-level thinking.

Planning Required to Make VLE’s More Inclusive

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The pandemic's unplanned remote teaching experiences necessitated critical reflection on the "best practices" for differentiation, assessment and evaluation. Conditions for learning remained the foundation of building effective classrooms. We learned that knowing our students deeply remained paramount to their wellbeing and achievement (Friedrich & Perrotta, 2022; Sider, et al., 2021). We also learned that supporting our neurodivergent learners in virtual environments had significant challenges and opportunities (Sider et al., 2021). VLE's are now permanent structures in publicly funded school districts across Canada. For this reason, there is an imperative for teachers to get this right. VLE's must be more inclusive than the first iterations.

Inclusive education is a term often thrown around in educational settings. It means different things to different people; therefore, it is important to understand how I am using the term. For the purpose of this paper, inclusive education refers to the integration of students with learning exceptionalities into the learning of the classroom in authentic ways. This integration must be done with sensitivity so that all students see themselves as welcome members of a classroom.

Leveraging the technology available within the VLE classroom can service students with exceptionalities invisibly to other students (McHolm, 2023). The public nature of in-person differentiation, with its negative socio-emotional impact for neurodivergent learners has long been established (Katz, Sokal & Wu, 2021; Laplanche-Carey, 2019). But now, invisibly embedded through the technology found in the VLE, a virtual teacher can scaffold learning opportunities in the private domain. Methods such as flipped classrooms can prepare children for whole and small group discussions. Assistive technology (e.g., voice-to-text or text-to-voice) can allow students to

access information to get the information that neurodivergent learners need (He, et al. 2022; Merrit, 2019; Satsangi). Students that struggle with distractibility, self-regulation; those that are medically fragile, have anxiety or uncontrollable physical behaviours (e.g., twitches, seizures, stereotypies etc.) can briefly turn cameras off, and thereby protect their sense of self when they are uncomfortable (Stalmach et al., 2023). The learning differences, that were so public in traditional classrooms, now do not have to be. Much of the students' essential differentiation, now, can be seamless and invisible to others. The task of learning is not easier for the neurodivergent or Multi-Language Learner (MLL) in the VLE. But what it does permit is rehearsal and recursive review of materials provided in the VLE. A student can slow down or speed up videos. They can re-watch things multiple times. These are accommodations that cannot be naturally done in the brick-and-mortar classroom. This technological privacy has the potential to serve neurodivergent learners greatly.

Teachers are still struggling to find novel ways to re-direct students back to assigned tasks. The standard in-person technique of proximity to the student as re-direction, is now being placed with pop-ups alerting students to get back on task. (A teacher can see up to eight or 10 screens on a secondary monitor and thereby tell who is working on the correct tab). As the VLE continues to evolve, more AI generated monitoring will act as a tool for maintaining on-task behaviour. But all of these technological advances only work if the student is both online and on-screen. When students disengage and leave the room or does not even log on, the VLE teacher is still grappling for supports.

Simple Tips to Maximize Adaptive Tools in the VLE

The power of the VLE is the ever-expanding array of pug-ins or add-ons. By the time this article is in circulation, several new adaptive tools will be available to increase ease of differentiation. It is important to teach or review the following adaptive supports in the VLE. At the same time more precision and less public knowledge of a student's accommodations or needed modifications. The VLE offers so much potential in this realm. (But this assumes that secondary assistance is not required to keep the student on task – just good teaching. I acknowledge that that might not be the reality in many of our VLE classrooms). Tasks in the VLE offer many advantages to the in-person classroom for Multi-Language Learners (MLL) and neurodivergent learners.

As student tasks are created, VLE educators must normalize these adaptive tools for all learners. Simple steps of having all students turn on their closed caption can make a difference. It can act as real time translation (for Multi-Language Learners) or individuals that need to see the words to understand (Hard-of-hearing or Deaf students; those with verbal processing disorders). The pacing options available through flipped classroom methods, slowing recordings down when viewing, the use of screen readers, Speech-to-text plugins, repetitious viewing and sound cancelling headphones all assist the student with learning differences. Chunking assignments into 10-15 minutes or less, for younger learners, will help those with focus and attentional issues. Using systems to create transcripts for students that need them can happen easily. Creating different approaches for information delivery allow for your creativity to shine and will keep the interest of your students high (He, et al., 2022; Hollingshead & Carr-Chellman, 2019). Student-centred collaborative

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projects with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGUL) will naturally include students with disabilities into the learning. The setting up of a VLE that keeps inclusive education in mind, will always centre student learning, their strengths, and their tenacity. But teachers must move from good ideas to committed actions of digital space learning. Before assessment, must come sound pedagogy grounded in Universal Design Learning (UDL).

Planned Types of Interactions (Teacher-Student, Student-Student)

One of the most notable areas of growth I saw in teachers during the pandemic, was how they began to plan the types of interactions that educators wanted to see students having with other students and with teachers. Initially I saw a lot of whole class instruction, and then small group instruction where other students were offline, and then over time, I saw more student group work and teachers managing those pieces as if floating around an in-person classroom. This must be a part of the productive, inclusive virtual classroom.

In the brick-and-mortar classroom, we would not solely rely on written assessments or slide shows as demonstrations of student learning. Therefore, we should not accept that in the virtual classroom either. The interactive aspect within the VLE is critical to confirming that the students themselves have done the learning. When you match the task purpose with the assessment modality and then couple it with the type of interaction, deeper assessment data will inform your teaching. Including online demonstrations, exhibitions, observations, oral assessment, peer assessments, performance assessments, portfolio assessments, student self-assessments, and self-reflections are all feasible

within the VLE (Merrit, 2019). The teacher can make use of the anecdotal records, transcripts, video recordings, photos of #D models, concept maps, in-class debates, debriefing (such as the self-and-match), graphic organizers, multimedia presentations, performance samples, individual and group products (e.g., letters, essays, tests, paintings, reports, journal writing, logs, online surveys, ticket out the door surveys, stories) and student-teacher conferences. All of these examples transfer easily into the VLE. Using one slide deck, small groups may work on individual slides when students are stuck, the teacher then allows them to look at others slides, then returning to their slide before finalizing their work. The interesting thing is that all these quality assessment options are available in both brick-and-mortar and VLE classrooms. The difference might be the technological tools necessary to facilitate collaboration.

Learner-Instructor interactions or student-to-teacher interactions are the facilitation type where educators feel most confident. These direct observations, antidotal records of comments and visible learning that students are doing in the presence of the teacher. Observations become an essential point for the triangulation of data for VLE assessment. There is a growing number of facilitation tools in the VLE that will assist in assessment. With plugin tools that create transcripts, teachers are now able to have a document of conversations in breakout rooms alongside with the keystroke changes on documents. Although not widely used yet, smart technology available in higher education (e.g., ViLLE and hypothes.is), can filter documents based upon pre-determined key words. Such tools could help all teachers in the future to understand where their students are spending their time, and uncover their misconceptions. But it will only be a realistic possibility

once such tools are readily available. Post-facilitation, these tools act as documentation not interaction. Caprara and Caprara (2022) reminds us that transformative learning happens during synchronous facilitation-interactions with feedback.

Practices of timely, descriptive feedback is crucial in the online learning environment.

Communication can take many forms, depending upon the size of your classroom and your role.

Using email groups for reminders of outstanding assignments or upcoming tests are effective ways to keep communication open, particularly with families. Small group instruction, individual instruction reinforce students' understanding of your expectations. This will lead to greater learner independence.

The most powerful feedback is given when it is specific to what the student should continue to do, what their next steps are and how to reach their proximal learning goal. The only way to give that three-fold descriptive feedback is when the educator knows precisely what the next step should be.

Learning is not strictly unidirectional sequential. There are many ways to get to the same place.

Therefore, flexible, homogenous targeted learning groups are important avenues to create differentiated and tailored instruction for VLE students.

The most powerful type of VLE interactions is learner-to-learner or peer-to-peer learning. When done properly, this learning gives the educator the most assessment data. Building co-dependent learning is important for creating community. In many in-person classrooms there is a structure to "ask a friend" before asking the teacher. This can be replicated in the VLE. Develop leadership in

your classroom through peer-to-peer questions boards. Student monitors of this public question board can answer each other's questions, and/or bring to the teacher's attention patterns of questions. By empowering students to assist each other in structured ways, the students responding deepen their own learning. (This public question board archive common questions about assignments – important for future tweaking). At the end of a class, a quick review of these questions can be used before a ticket out the door, or to summarize key learning.

Wyatt-Smith and Adie (2021) emphasized the importance of students' peer evaluative expertise. In the VLE, the teacher must create the conditions of the learning environment to support this journey towards improvement. Students from giving and receiving feedback. This must be scaffolded through structured methods (e.g., two stars and a wish for primary children) to more structured feedback using assessment rubrics for older students. By explicitly teaching what a student is looking for and self-assessing their work, with the teacher using the same rubric for assessment, the teacher and student can conference on where there was alignment and where there was discrepancy. Formatting this self-assessment as a self-and-match, students are encouraged to honestly reflect on their work. This looks like the student believes that they got a level 2 on a section, and the teacher agrees. In the discussion with the teacher, if they can explain why, it was a 2 and not a 3, then the student gets two-points – one for the matching assessment and one for understanding why. If the student says they got a level 4 but the teacher believes that the student received a level 1, then the student has the opportunity to explain why they feel it should be assessed at a higher level. It is in these deeper conversations about assessment, that the student

starts to become more aware of their work. This form of self-and-match assessment is time consuming, but it acts as clear method for the student to bring forward what their “next-step goals” in upcoming learning. These “next-step goals” can be filed in a VLE document so that they can review them before starting the next assignment. As they achieve these goals, the teacher can edit the list of next steps or can review it when creating report card comments. (This is quick way to personalized report cards, which is both meaningful and manageable). These “self-and-match” scores can be added to a classroom “virtual reward bank”; increasing the relevance of peer-to-peer rubric review before submitting work. Too often culminating tasks feedback are rarely internalized by the student. Too much value is placed upon the mark rather than the actual feedback. This method, therefore augments student and teacher co-reflection. As the students become more skilled using this reflection technique, your conferencing will become more efficient and their learning will be deepened.

The practices of good pedagogy, good instruction and good evaluation transcends all learning environments. When done well, it is inclusive, differentiated and gives opportunities to extend the learning for those students that are ready for it. Although the VLE has a different delivery context, the same practices apply, as they do for brick-and-mortar classrooms.

Assessment Considerations

When considering how and what you are assessing, remember to be specific about your activity’s pedagogical goal (e.g., social annotation versus a conversation thread). Are you attempting to build

understanding or evoke reflection? Think about the tools that select for certain tasks. Tools such as Diigo (allows a student to colour code important ideas, concurring ideas and opposition ones separately. The document can then create a summary document under those headings). Be aware that Crowd Layering (process of multiple students actively highlighting on the same document) can be distracting for young or distractable learners.

Engagement Through Application and Gamification

Educators across North America have been drawn to the use of games in all types of classrooms.

In the Virtual Environment (VE) careful consideration of all applications in use must happen. Too often “freebies” are not free. They are advertising platforms disguised as educational tools. Many of these games, do not align with curricular expectations, and have been created for the American educational market. We must be judicious with our use of “educational games” in the classroom.

Too many students how that addictive nature of some online games for children and teens (Kuss & Griffiths, 2012; Rosendo-Rios & Shukla, 2022; Rahayu et al., 2020) and have been linked to negative mental health outcomes (David et al, 2020; Li et al., 2022). But the allure of gamification to both students and their teachers trying to engage their students is real.

If you are using gamification or digital-game-based-learning (DGBL), follow district guidelines for product use. (Many districts are developing digital resource policies that limit the use of games when personal accounts are required). That said, students playing games without purpose, will lose

their value. Concerns related to the gamification were summarized by Tseklevs et al. (2016) to eight possible pitfalls:

- 1) Game and curriculum alignment
- 2) Clearly supporting intended assessment
- 3) Providing enhanced learning opportunities for students, rather than just a source of “fun”
- 4) “Transferability” learning to real-life situations.
- 5) Technical challenges associated with the design and development of serious games
- 6) Game platform maintenance and support
- 7) Production costs “associated game development;” and
- 8) Promotion and distribution of games” (p. 168)

The use of educational games and simulations acts as a potential additional opportunity for student learning in the VLE.

Educational games can be used to consolidate knowledge and explore simulations. Limited budgets in social sciences and STEM classes have embraced simulators. Virtual Reality applications can make otherwise impossible trips to Europe or to the sea floor autonomously controlled by the student possible. Other times, gamification is not used to its full potential. Many of the games, do not align with curricular expectations, and have been created for the American educational market. Some of the most commonly used educational games show promise (e.g., Dreambox, Booklet, Quizlet, Baamboozle, ABC Kids, Education Galaxy, Funbrain, GameUp, Kahoot, GoNoodle, Lexia, Quest Atlantis, Backyard Engineers, Planet Mechanic and GeoNet). With each passing day more DGBL come online. The tools listed have completed or are beginning evidence-based testing. If used correctly, gamification can bolster the student’s ability to demonstrate learning in a specified area.

Feedback and Assessment in the Virtual Learning Environment

There is much to be hopeful in the digital learning space. Evidence has shown that it is possible to use this learning environment to the advantage of students' interests and needs (Bishop, 2021; Gallagher & Cottingham, 2020). Teachers reported knowing their students more deeply, having more self-pacing options, understanding homelife realities more clearly and being able to provide more individualized choice and programming (Bishop, 2021).

Assessment in the virtual environment still follows the forms of assessment found in brick-and-mortar classrooms. It is divided into three categories of diagnostic, formative and summative. Diagnostic and formative assessment can be based on single data points to guide proximal teaching-points. Summative assessments or culminating assessment, must have the triangulation of data (observation, process and product). VLE diagnostics include: conversations, observations, video conference platform polls, the use of shared brainstorming tools (e.g., Jamboards (K-12), Kidspiration Maps (K-3), Popplet (1-12), Mural (K-12), Coggle (5-12), Prezi (6-12), Miro (8-12)) to invite conversation and shared thinking.

Using social annotation tools can provide deeper learning opportunities and formative assessment for the educator. Social annotation is the process of reading and thinking together. In the VLE, educators have struggled to do this naturally. But it is a critical way to enhance cognition and communal growth (Kuznetcova, Lin & Glaman, 2021; Qushem et al., 2021). Without in-person non-verbal cues, physical movements, full body language observation, eye contact and subtle facial expressions, it is hard for the teacher in the VLE to know organically who to call on.

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Particularly many diverse students will need additional assurances, as their self-identity is less transparent in the VLE social context (Vorobel, Voorhees & Gokcora, 2018). According to Kuznetcova, Lin and Glaman (2021) the types of social annotation include: supporting arguments, inquiry, reflection and knowledge construction. Research supported that it also improves literacy skills when students are asked to question and predict outcomes. The Diigo tool has shown that social bookmarking and annotation deepens understanding and builds visible collaboration that is easily tracked (Di Mele & Ranieri, 2020; Li & Lai, 2022; Vorobel, Voorhees & Gokcora, 2018). It also has shown that it focuses students' questions, can improve literacy levels and supports accessibility collaboration (Di Mele & Ranieri, 2020; Li & Lai, 2022). This is but one example of the transformative power now available in the VLE.

Digital spaces also allow for Precision Education (PE). This term was coined to indicate the dissecting of curricula expectations into "micro-lessons" so that students get precisely what they need to advance to the next proximal learning point (Qushem, et al., 2021). The opportunity to have education tailored very specifically to individual student needs can be done in face-to-face learning environments, but not without a social cost to students working below grade level (Jacobs & Mantiri, 2022). Within the virtual learning environment, this is not the case. Appropriate diagnostic assessments can pinpoint the barriers or false-understandings. Then the micro-lesson is employed to address this need. For example, the Past Test (a publicly available diagnostic literacy assessment found at www.pasttest.com), indicates specific literacy errors for emergent and struggling readers. Resources like *Equipped for Reading Success* contain one-minute interventions

that educators can use to help the student develop that required skill (Kirpatrick, 2016). The intervention is a small-time commitment and gives the student specific skill development that will address precise gaps in their understanding and all of this can happen in a private breakout room. This is not only doable from an assessment and learning standpoint, but it also respects the needs of the struggling student.

Small steps of embedded small group instruction and intervention are possible in the VLE. It is imperative that as educators, we not only consider what we teach, but how we teach. Our professional stance to learning requires us to do better, as we know better. The experiment of remote pandemic learning shone a light on the possible inequities of VLE learning environments, but it also showed that there were many possibilities for learners in the VLE classrooms. By incorporating aspects of PICRAT and utilizing accommodating tools easily embedded in the VLE, we can address more of the learning needs of our students.

Conclusion

With the expansion of VLE environments in Canada and around the world, it is critical that we consider deeply the context of learning and how that impacts teacher decision-making and student outcomes. By scrutinizing the TPACK and PIRCAT frameworks, the importance of both teacher-centred knowledge and student-centred activities are clear. No one framework can encompass the complexities of teaching within the VLE. Although TPACK is well-researched and criticised, its relevance to today's classrooms in the virtual environment cannot be over-emphasized. VLE teachers must begin with specific content, pedagogical and technological knowledge in order to

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deliver inclusive programs for an increasingly diverse student body. Equally, attention must be given to the PICRAT framework of the type of learning that students ideally make in the classroom. This newer framework supports the VLE by focusing on the student, rather than the teacher. That transition of teaching and learning was an important evolution within the VLE during the pandemic. This article offered models and tools to assist VLE teachers with a point of engagement, while embedding inclusion, in order to reach more diverse student learners.

Learning in the VLE offers many of the same opportunities and possible pitfalls as in-person classrooms. It requires the educator to be thoughtful about how they allot synchronous learning times, paired/small group versus whole class instruction and assessment processes. Abundantly evident, all teachers need to build inclusive classrooms where they know the learning needs and strengths of their students. The most successful teachers carefully consider the frameworks, content and assessment of their classrooms. The power of VLE is how seamlessly an educator can delivery differentiated work for the accommodated student without a social cost. It also allows students that need repetition or more processing time, options to do that learning in a way that is most effective for them. Keeping students engaged in the VLE can be struggle, but with variety in content, pedagogically sound tasks and creativity the students will find the openness of their learning empowering. Preparing students to learn in the virtual world will advantage many students with the competencies necessary to success in 21st Century work realities.

There is much to be hopeful in the digital learning space. It currently can support many types of learners, but more work needs to be done. Although some accommodations can be seamless in the

virtual classroom, many of students with exceptionalities struggle in the VLE. This is not to suggest that they cannot be successful in these contexts when shepherded through with a thoughtful, inclusive VL educator. We must overcome the many barriers that this modality of learning presents for marginalized students. The pandemic taught us that without great preparation of both the educators and the students for the Virtual Learning Environment, many students were left out. Despite the shortcomings of the VLE, many opportunities also present themselves for a wider variety of learners. Adaptations, flexibility, precision program delivery and modifications are the greatest power within the VL environment.

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